

**O‘ZBEKISTON RESPUBLIKASI OLIY TA‘LIM, FAN VA
INNOVATSIYALAR VAZIRLIGI**

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**“FAN VA TEXNIKANING RIVOJLANISHIDA ZAMONAVIY
AXBOROT TEXNOLOGIYALARINING O‘RNI”**

mavzusidagi xalqaro ilmiy-texnikaviy anjumani

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IMPROVEMENT OF TEACHING MATERIALS IN THE TEACHING OF FUNDAMENTAL SCIENCES OF METROLOGY AND STANDARDIZATION ON THE BASIS OF IMITATION-VARIATION

Doniyor Baxodirovich Xamidov, Jamshidbek G‘ayratjon o‘g‘li Obidov.

Annotation: The article discusses the development and improvement of teaching materials for the teaching of fundamental sciences of metrology and standardization. It focuses on the use of the imitation-variation approach, which helps students develop a deeper understanding of the subject matter. The authors explore the current challenges and propose strategies to enhance the effectiveness of teaching through the use of imitation, variation, and modeling activities. The study highlights the importance of providing hands-on experiences and real-life examples to engage students and improve learning outcomes.

Keywords: teaching materials, fundamental sciences, metrology, standardization, imitation-variation, teaching strategies, modeling activities, learning outcomes.

СОВЕРШЕНСТВОВАНИЕ УЧЕБНЫХ МАТЕРИАЛОВ В ПРЕПОДАВАНИИ ФУНДАМЕНТАЛЬНЫХ НАУК МЕТРОЛОГИИ И СТАНДАРТИЗАЦИИ НА ОСНОВЕ ИМИТАЦИИ-ВАРИАЦИИ

Хамидов Дониёр Баксодирович, Джамшидбек Гайратжон оглы Обидов.

Аннотация: В статье рассматривается разработка и совершенствование учебно-методических материалов для преподавания фундаментальных наук метрологии и стандартизации. Основное внимание уделяется использованию имитационно-вариационного подхода, который помогает учащимся глубже понять предмет. Авторы исследуют текущие проблемы и предлагают стратегии повышения эффективности обучения за счет использования имитации, вариации и моделирования. Исследование подчеркивает важность предоставления практического опыта и примеров из реальной жизни для вовлечения студентов и улучшения результатов обучения.

Ключевые слова: учебные материалы, фундаментальные науки, метрология, стандартизация, имитационно-вариативность, стратегии обучения, моделирование деятельности, результаты обучения.

Introduction. Different methods to be understandable to the student in teaching independent education a lesson is taught through. This thing arouses

interest in the student. As a result of this interest in science will increase, after which the result will be known. When teaching innovative technologies, the first thing that matters is how it is taught is considered.

The concept of method is also different from the concept of style quality independent education to the student or learner using the methods is said to deliver. The concept of method is not only Language learning is different are also used in the fields.

Imitation through innovative methods models can be created because the method virtual resources how realizes and ensures that it is referred to. Therefore, when creating virtual resources through simulation models, it is necessary to pay attention not only to its educational methodical views, but also to its normative content. Because its direction is defined through content. Creating a structure and creating a process is formed on the basis of imitation-variability.

In the process of building a simulation model, selecting topics from specialized disciplines, especially innovative technologies, and moving image graphs to them, this means that it is fully implemented, and its modeling environment and the simulator that make it up are shown in Figure 1 below . Because the last process is only a verification process, it remains only to use the finished model in practice.

Educational modeling environments (eng. Education modeling) Every simulation term that is used in general in the training of future engineers-metrologists or product quality managers, whose professional functions are now quite common, is called "man-machine". Ensuring the maximum approximation to reality, for example, allows engineers in the field of technical higher education to develop optimal decisions and various educational trajectories , its aspects and corresponding cognitive criteria [1].

Research methodology. Regular and non-standard professional situations mainly provide the formation of target imitative variability in the future quality education or independent education. It serves to clarify the role of the student in the learning process.

A large part of modern professional educational practices, in one way or another, is a dynamic, complex structure related to the provision of simulation-variability and represents a certain risk for the engineer, and often in the scientific literature "engineer-machine" intelligence. the so-called environment. This situation explains the great interest of specialists in the field of vocational education. The studied professional systems consist of the development of active

and interactive educational technologies in the simulation environment, which are replaced by their models, and their integration into the pedagogical process.

The development of simulated learning environments is not only in the independent learning process, but also for the traditional educational process in digital education [2]. Their design in the form of software is carried out before work, which summarizes and schematizes positive and negative professional experience. analysts, the role of teachers in the implementation of causal relations and relations of learning, and the integration of a large variety of skills into the learning process and the final environments, thus demonstrating the formation of a holistic didactic system [3] .

Results. Today, the rapid development of the innovative sector in the life of society, the growth of the share of intellectual products, information and scientific-technical and innovative activities in the economy has led to the fact that innovations, like minerals, production capacities and intellectual potential, are considered the wealth of the country. Effective use of innovative and scientific and technical potential for the benefit of our country and its citizens would not have been possible without the formation of a comprehensive innovation policy in the country and the creation of legislative foundations for its implementation.

Figure 1. Variation in Measurement System | Various Types & Examples

With the implementation of market reforms, the integration of the country into the world community, the change of the world economic system towards the growth of the role of knowledge and information, the strengthening of relations between new technologies and the capital market, the transition of our country's economy to the path of innovative development becomes of urgent importance.

Knowledge of the general laws and trends of development in the leading developed and developing countries of the world, as well as taking into account

the unique conditions of Uzbekistan, which has rich natural resources, production and scientific and technical potential, can lead to the path of innovative development of Uzbekistan. ways and methods can be developed. Due to the commercialization of intellectual products in the modern world, a fundamental change in the role of science and technology, each country, as well as structures at the lower management level up to the level of individual enterprises, allocate resources to scientific and technical and innovative activities in market conditions, and their attitude to the implementation of the results of these activities. must have a vision, that is, develop its own innovative policy that will allow effective achievement of the set socio-economic goals of the country, region, organization and individual [4].

Conclusion and suggestions. The results of a number of scientific studies related to the theory of teaching and this field show that today teaching is carried out mainly based on traditional explanatory methods. The creation of hypertext, hypermedia, graphics and computer sound programs makes it possible not only to effectively use information technologies in the educational system, but also to organize non-traditional lessons on science topics. When analyzing the process of teaching on the basis of computer technologies in higher educational institutions of advanced foreign countries and leading educational institutions of our republic, several directions can be seen [5].

Based on simulation-variability Improved modeling based on simulation-variability based on simulation-variability is researching objects of knowledge (physical phenomena and processes) using their models improved on the basis of simulation-variability, making and studying improved models of existing subjects and events based on simulation-variability . On the basis of imitation-variation based on imitation-variation the method of improved modeling on the basis of imitation-variation is widely used in modern science. In the process of independent education, the didactic features of the formation of educational materials on the basis of imitation-variation in the teaching of specialized subjects to students facilitate the process of scientific research, and in some cases become the only means of studying complex objects.

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